

THE DEVELOPMENT OF TEACHER ICT COMPETENCE

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Abstract. *The article shows that modern ICT greatly expands educational opportunities. Such modern technologies as blogs, wiki, podcasts, e-mail and web-forum can contribute to the development of foreign language students' discourse skills. This paper deals with modern information and communication technologies, which are used quite often in every day's life: e-mail, web forum, blogs, wikis and podcasts. In the Internet, there are many other modern ICTs. However, these are chosen to confine that are most likely to be used for the discourse skills development in a language school.*

Keywords: technologies, games, e-mail, internet, blogs, laptops.

РАЗВИТИЕ ИКТ-КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ УЧИТЕЛЯ

Аннотация. *В статье показано, что современные ИКТ значительно расширяют образовательные возможности. Такие современные технологии, как блоги, вики, подкасты, электронная почта и веб-форум, могут способствовать развитию навыков дискурсивной речи у студентов-иностранцев. В статье рассматриваются современные информационные и коммуникационные технологии, которые довольно часто используются в повседневной жизни: электронная почта, веб-форум, блоги, вики и подкасты. В Интернете существует множество других современных ИКТ. Тем не менее, они выбраны, чтобы ограничить те, которые, скорее всего, будут использоваться для развития навыков общения в языковой школе.*

Ключевые слова: технологии, игры, электронная почта, интернет, блоги, ноутбуки.

People have conducted in-depth research on using technology to change the teaching environment, and the technology has become an important part of science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) education. Schools and teachers must be in a good position to adapt to the changing curriculum and use information and communication technology (ICT) for teaching. However, since in-service teachers may not have received STEM education in their teacher preparation courses, continuous professional development (PD) is a way to make changes. This document describes the progress of teachers' proficiency and confidence in the four selected Web 2.0 tools (Skype video conferencing tool, email, blog, and Wiki) when participating in the STEM ICT PD program. The first phase brought together two series of face-to-face seminars. Participants included 86 teachers from 25 carefully selected nurseries, primary and secondary schools in Trinidad. The hybrid approach is used to collect data through Web 2.0 tools, online questionnaires, and paperbased ICT self-competitiveness checklists. Analysis shows that all teachers have used these four Web 2.0 tools to make progress in their level. The improvement in confidence can be clearly seen from the teachers' self-reports and their positions. They explained that their self-confidence level is none, low or high. The highest level of proficiency comes from working in a digitally rich environment in a professional development center rather than usually in a school with fewer digital resources. The moderator's support has also increased capacity and confidence, especially during the face-to-face component of the performance data. ICT PD has made recommendations for gradually improving STEM education

and for school leaders to improve their school's digital environment.

Today's education is affected by large-scale changes such as globalization and internationalization. The economic and intellectual development of a country is related to the ability of the education system to respond to the changing needs of post-industrial society and to meet the ability to provide high-quality modern education. Education in science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) has been placed on the global agenda as a mechanism to promote 21st century skills such as communication, collaboration, problem solving, creativity and critical thinking. Even in a small country like Trinidad and Tobago, STEM education is recommended as a way to cultivate highly skilled and skilled workforce to successfully promote its oil and gas based economy.

Different authors affirm that it is very important to consider the use of technology because it provides students with a more personalized experience and support during the learning process (Ruthven, 2003, as mentioned in the quote. This is an important aspect of learning from languages, namely: comments and language). Marsh (2012) cited Ruthven (2003), who also noted that ICT activities can promote greater student participation in a less stressful environment; The author also pointed out that by using ICT tools, teachers can achieve better results. Multiple learning methods and promote independent and collaborative learning.

Information and communication technologies change the way students think and learn by supporting adventure and knowledge sharing. These technologies are fast, automated, interactive and multi-modal, and allow students to control the way and time of learning. Specific requirements will change based on people's need to find solutions to problems or establish and communicate learning. The Commonwealth of Australia's ideas on ICT in education are probably the most enlightening because it involves students, their attitudes, interests, and their ideas. It can be said that educational technology can satisfy all aspects and knowledge interests of students because they can control certain aspects of the learning process. Because of the students' discourse ability, it is necessary to understand a specific set of knowledge and skills that students need to learn a foreign language in order to encode information and decode syntax rules according to the vocabulary, grammar and language of the foreign language. Taking into account the stylistic, gender, sociocultural, psychological and emotional factors, and achieve the communication goals through cohesion and continuity. Through the initial stage of this study, it was possible to determine that students from this context prefer activities that involve the use of ICT and oral production when learning the foreign language. Thus, designing or adapting materials or workshops in order to fit learners' preferences becomes a challenge and a must in our teaching practices. It is worth mentioning that when learners' needs and interests are considered in the classroom, "learning becomes an easier and faster process" (Dudley-Evans & St John, 1998; Fiorito, 2005; Hutchinson & Waters, 1987; Krashen, 1981; as cited in). Constant reflection and planning is necessary, if we want to help our students to be successful in their learning process. There are priceless benefits when we consider the particular needs and interests of a group when designing and implementing classes and activities.

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